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On the geographical distribution and bionomics of *Grapholita nigrostriana* (Snellen, 1883): First observation in Hungary (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae)

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Abstract. The first observation of *Grapholita nigrostriana* (Tortricidae) in Hungary is reported. The study describes the diagnosis, the bionomics, and the geographical distribution of the species. Sightings in Poland and Slovakia are also discussed. Diagnostic markers for the identification of the species are presented in photographs and diagrams. The distribution of the species in central Europe is shown on a map.

Keywords. Lepidoptera, Tortricidae, *Grapholita nigrostriana*, biology, distribution, Hungary

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Introduction

The genus *Grapholita* Treitschke, 1829 comprises about 130–140 described species worldwide (Brown 2005). The majority of described species occur in the Holarctic. However, this might reflect a lack of collecting and taxonomic study in other regions (particularly the Afrotropical and Neotropical regions) rather than the actual paucity of *Grapholita* species in those areas (Rota & Brown 2009). According to Razowski (2003) the genus contains c90 species of which the majority (c40) are Palearctic in distribution, with 19 currently known in Europe. The larvae of the majority of the species feed on species of Leguminosae, though a few affect Cannabaceae. They live mainly in the stems of plants and feed on the seeds within the pods and the winter is passed as a fully-grown larva.

So far, 20 species of genus *Grapholita* are known to occur in Hungary (Pastoralis & Buschmann 2018). The geographical distribution and bionomics of only a few species have been studied and there is no comprehensive monograph on the genus.

Most Hungarian authors use the image plates of the Razowski books of Tortricidae for identification, using hand magnifiers. This is scientifically inappropriate. These anomalies have already been pointed out by Agassiz (2002). In his book review of Razowski (2001), Agassiz (2002: 153) put together in a table all the misidentifications/image permutations and uncertainties recognized by various experts in that book. The genus *Grapholita* was hit particularly hard in the moth illustrations.

In this study, I identify *Grapholita nigrostriana* from Hungary by genital examination. This is the first observation of this species from this country. I describe the vegetation of the habitat at the capture site, describe the distribution of the foodplant in Hungary and provide a thumbnail sketch of the species' localities in Poland, Slovakia, and Hungary.

Material and methods

Adult moths were caught by hand-netting after being disturbed from vegetation during the afternoon. Genitalia preparations were made according to Robinson (1976). For some examples, the genitalia were mounted in Euparal on slides; others were preserved in micro-vials filled with glycerol. The images (see Plate x) were taken with a Sony DSC-H100v camera and a BMS tCam 5.0 MP digital camera mounted on a Zeiss stereo microscope using ScopePhoto 3.0.12 software. Genitalia photographs were taken with an Olympus ECE TR biological microscope and a MicroQ 3.0 MP digital camera connected to a computer at 20x and 50x magnification. The resulting habitus and genitalia photos were analysed using Corel Draw/Paint and Photoshop. The identified specimens are deposited in the following collections:

- Gábor Pastorális (private collection, SK-Komárno)
- Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest
- Ignác Richter (private collection, SK-Malá Čausa)
- Museum Košice (SK- Košice)
- Pannon Intézet, Pécs | Pannon Institute, Pécs,
- Zdenko Tokar (private collection, SK-Sal'a)

Results

Grapholita nigrostriana (Snellen, 1883) (Figs 1–5, 15.)

Grapholita nigrostriana Snellen, 1883, Tijdschr. Ent., 26: 223, pl. 13., figs 6, 6a. Type locality: Far East (Russia [Albasin]). Original description based on a male specimen.

References: Agassiz 2002; Buszko & Nowacki 2017; Brown 2005; Danilevsky & Kuznetsov 1968; Fazekas 2002; Fazekas 2007; Kennel 1921; Razowski 2001; Razowski 2003; Rota & Brown 2009; Sinev 2019.

Diagnosis. Wingspan 10,5–14 mm. The labial palpi are silky white, the frons slightly reddish. There is a white ring on the abdomen laterally and ventrally. The forewing has a brownish to slightly bronze base colour and the basal area is usually paler than the median part and there are black lines inside the distal half of the median cell. Forewing markings are reduced to costal and subterminal parts of deep brown median fascia. A whitish dorsal patch at one half arises at 90 degrees to the wing edge and immediately and distinctly bends towards the wing apex; it contains a thin and wavy brownish line along the mid-line. A more or less crescent-shaped plumbeous strigula arises from approximately the third costal strigula and curves distally between the apex of the dorsal patch and the apex of the forewing to terminate in the area of the (absent) ocellus. The terminal cilia are brownish and not interrupted by post apical strigula. The hind wing is brownish to brownish with whitish cilia beyond a dark brown basal line. It is a variable species, in particular with regard to the shape of the dorsal patch, which may be pale or darker.

Male genitalia (Figs 6-9, 14-16.). The valva very short, with a deep ventral incision. Cucullus elongate, rounded terminally. The angle of the sacculus is rounded and the margin is sclerotized. Aedeagus more or less bottle-shaped, sometimes slightly bulging in the middle, narrower apically, with 12-15 small cornuti.

Note: in Razowski (2001, 2003; pl. 42, 436), the aedeagus is depicted as lacking cornuti. In Danilevsky and Kuznetsov (1968: p. 618, Fig. 532), the genitalia of the aedeagus have the small cornutus. The cornuti are clearly visible in the Slovakian specimen (see Fig. 00, Richter, genital slide no. 32567, SK-Komárno).

Female genitalia (Figs 11–12.). The female is not known from Hungary; the description here is based on Razowski (2003): Sterigma weakly sclerotized on postostial part, colliculum membranous. In the ductus bursae, signa are absent. The female genitalia habitus is clearly distinguishable from that of similar species.

Note: The female genitalia are represented differently in Danilevsky and Kuznetsov (1968) and Razowski (2003, pl. 87, 436.). A photograph of a real microscope slide would be needed to resolve the anomalies.

Similar species. *Grapholita discretana* (Wocke, 1861), *G. pallifrontana* ([Liebig] & Zeller, 1846). Many ecological and geographical forms of these two species are known. It is only possible to distinguish damaged and worn specimens of these from *G. nigrostrigana* by examining the genitalia.

Biology. According to the literature the larva feeds on *Astragalus cicer* and is monophagous, though it is possible that it also lives on other foodplants. The exact flight times of the adult are not known. The Hungarian moths were collected in May and June. They fly to light, but can be disturbed from vegetation during the day and are easy to collect. In Hungary, they were found in dry grassland, *Arrhenatherum* hay meadows, coniferous forests and plantations mixed with native deciduous trees and dry and semi-dry pioneer scrub.

Geographical distribution. It is distributed from the Amur River region, trans-Palaearctic to central Europe, but is mostly a highly fragmented species. Major geographical occurrences

Figs 1–5. *Grapholita nigrostriana*:
Snellen's original illustrations (details enlarged);
1. lateral view of the head, 2. habitus of the wings.

Habitus photos of the first specimen of *Grapholita nigrostriana* in Hungary (Nagymányok);
3. the head in lateral view, 4. wing pattern with details enlarged, 5. the abdomen in lateral view.

Note: There are differences in the forewing pattern between the “Snellen-type” specimen and the Hungarian specimen.

Pieter Cornelius Tobias **Snellen** (1832–1911)

Figs 6–13. Male and female genitalia *Grapholita nigrostriana*:

6. ♂ genitalia, Hungary, Nagymányok, genital slide no. 3513. I. Fazekas.
7. ♂ genitalia, Hungary, Nagymányok, genital slide no. 3513. With higher magnification.
8. ♂ genitalia, Slovakia, Komárno, genital slide no. 32567. I. Richter,
9. ♂ genitalia, the valva is highlighted and enlarged.
10. ♂ genitalia after Danilevsky & Kuznetsov 1968.
11. ♀ genitalia after Danilevsky & Kuznetsov 1968.
12. ♀ genitalia after after Razowski 2001.
13. ♂ genitalia after Razowski 2001.

Note: in Razowski (2001, 2003) the aedeagus is depicted as lacking cornuti. In Danilevsky and Kuznetsov (1968) the genitalia of the aedeagus have the small cornutus. The cornuti are clearly visible in the Hungarian and Slovakian specimen.

Figs 14–16. *Grapholita nigrostriana*, ♂ genitalia; **14.** characteristic valva and cornutus shapes. **15.** Important diagnostic stamps of the forewing. **16.** Typical shape and specific form of the valva with markings.

based on literature affect the Amur region, the Far East, South Siberia, Kazakhstan, Ural Territory, Ukraine, Poland, Slovakia, and Hungary. Based on what is known so far, it reaches its westernmost limit of geographical distribution in the Carpathian Basin.

Distribution of Central-Europe

Hungary. New site in Hungary, data from the first observations: 3♂, HU-Nagymányok, 46.161980, 18.251717, 162 m, 17.05.2022. leg. et det. I. Fazekas, genital slide no. 3513. I. Fazekas (in coll. Pannon Institute, HU-Pécs).

The habitat area has a highly mosaic structure. A typical hilly landscape, where black coal mines have existed for two hundred years. The area is part of the Mecsek mountain range, with mountains 500-600 metres high in the south. Most of the area is protected by Natura 2000 and is a landscape conservation area. The mines have been closed for 30 years, equipment has been dismantled and the land recultivated. It is now mostly dominated by cereal crops (wheat, barley), and maize, with meadows, partly mown as pasture and cattle grazing, mostly along the valley stream to the north. The forests are planted, rather than naturally established. There is an extremely high proportion of pine and acacia, but also linden, maple and sessile oak. Before the Second World War, there were vineyards and orchards in the area, now indicated only by the presence of walnut trees and remnants of vines. The remains of lonely old lime trees indicate the presence of a pasture. The shrub layer of the woodland edges is composed of birch and hawthorn. *Acer tataricum* also occurs sporadically. The new Hungarian site at Nagymányok is 240

km south of the Slovak site (Komárno) as the crow flies and lies in Baranya County, close to the Croatian border. It is an agricultural and wine-growing area, bordered to the east by the River Danube and to the south by the River Dráva. Most of the county is mountainous (Mecsek Mountains, Villány Hills) and the mountains are bordered by continuous woodland, with the southern slopes dominated by karst scrub and rocky meadows. So far, eleven species of *Grapholita* have been recorded from the county, most of them exceedingly rare and local (Fazekas 2002, 2007).

Poland. Jaroslav Buszko reported on knowledge of this species in Poland. The specimen illustrated in Razowski (2003) was collected by J. Buszko, but the name of the locality (Katy, in the Pieniny Mountains) is incorrect – it is correctly Katy II near Zamość (Lublin Province). In the Buszko collection there is another specimen from the vicinity of Chelm (also from Lublin province): 04.06.2006.

Slovakia. Gábor Pastorális (SK-Komárno) reported that since 1987 he has collected several specimens in Slovakia, near the town of Komárno, at the confluence of the Danube and Váh (Waag in German and Vág in Hungarian) rivers.

Zdenko Tokár (pers. comm.) gave the sites around Komárno in the following form: Komárno (env. of the Danube river); 22.5.1989, 1 sp., 12.5.1996, 1 sp., 17.5.1999, 1 sp., leg. & det. G. Pastorális, 21.5.2010, 10 specimens, leg. & det. Z. Tokár, all coll. Z. Tokár. Šaľa (env. of the Váh river); 22.5.2006, 1 sp., 21.5.2010, 1 sp., 11.6.2020, 1 sp.

Ignác Richter collected 3 adult moths near the village of Hubovo in Slovakia. The site is only 3.5 km from the northern Hungarian border. My hypothesis is that the species should be further sought in the hilly and mountainous areas of northern Hungary. New data: Slovakia, Hubovo, 08-09. 05. 2009, 3 ex. leg. Ignác Richter, in coll. Museum Košice.

Andrej Reiprich verified the correctness of the identification by genital examination (see Reiprich 1989). Later, Ignác Richter also caught it in eastern Slovakia, near the Hungarian border, in the village of Hubovo. According to Pastorális, the imago flies around the food plant from the beginning to the end of May but does not move more than 5 metres away. It is thought that the larvae feed on seeds. Approximately 60 specimens are known from Slovakia, with voucher specimens in the private collections of Gábor Pastorális (SK-Komárno) and Ignác Richter (SK-Malá Čausa) and in the Hungarian Museum of Natural History in Budapest.

Notes on the foodplant

Astragalus cicer is widespread in Eurasia: native to Austria, Baltic States, Balkan, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Central European Rus, Czechoslovakia, East European Russia, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Crimea, North Caucasus, North European Russia, Northwest European Russia, Poland, Romania, South European Russia, Spain, Switzerland, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Ukraine, West Siberia. In Belarus, it is used to treat cardiovascular and gastrointestinal diseases (Lysiuk et al. 2016).

According to Király et al. (2009), *Astragalus cicer* is widespread in Hungary on the dry forest edges of hills and mountains, on field margins, and in secondary grasslands. In the lowlands, it occurs sporadically.

In North America, it is known from the following regions: Colorado, Denmark, Illinois, Indiana, Michigan, Minnesota, Montana, Nebraska, Nevada, New Mexico, Sweden, Utah, Washington, Wisconsin, Wyoming Ecology: moist grassy areas to open woodland, disturbed areas; Elevation: < 2000 m. Flowering Time: May–Aug.

(see <https://powo.science.kew.org/taxon/urn:lsid:ipni.org:names:476814-1>)

As the distribution data of the foodplant clearly show, *Grapholita nigrostriana* does not follow the European area of *Astragalus cicer* but breaks off in central Europe. There are certainly faunal and ecological reasons for this, which are not yet known. Geographical barriers to western colonization are unlikely but need to be looked for in the life history of the species and the study of ecological niches.

Figs 17–20.
Habitat of *Grapholita nigrostriana*
in Southern Hungary;
17. Mecsek Mountains, Nagymányok.
18–20. Different vegetation and
agricultural areas (mesophilic meadows,
pastures, plows, forest patches) in the
region, on limestone bedrock.

Fig. 21. The confirmed occurrences of *Grapholita nigrostriana* in Central Europe, with the boundaries of the area marked.

Fig. 22. Regional geographical distribution of *Grapholita nigrostriana* in Russia. The map is based on Sinev [ed.] 2019.

Conclusions

Populations in central Europe are highly isolated and the abundance of populations is unknown. There is no genetic link between the remaining populations on the periphery of the area in central Europe. This strongly influences and selects for genetic diversity. The European populations are endangered and further studies are needed. More thorough genital studies are needed to identify any sister *Grapholita* species. Species lists should be revised in those faunistic publications for which detailed studies have not been carried out.

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